

TRUST AND TRUSTWORTHINESS CODE BOOK

Introduction to coding

This document, which we call a “code book”, serves as the rulebook for classifying content for the presence/absence of **Trust** and **Trustworthiness** in interview data. This is similar to a labeling scheme for hand labeling a supervised machine learning model. When we say “code” it is the same as “applying a label or classification.” For this set of codes, you will be making decisions about the presence/absence of trust and trustworthiness for a **statement**, which is a collection of sentences on one general topic that has been separated into a unique paragraph. We are only coding the **statements** made by the interviewee (the person being interviewed), not the interviewer (the one asking the questions). Code each **statement** in the responses separately.

For this set of codes, we will be coding **congruent** mentions of our key concepts, which means we will code when an interviewee mentions one of our terms as we have defined it. In other words, we want to make a note if they are discussing something congruent with our concepts, even if they do not use the exact term “trust” or “trustworthiness.” However, we also want to capture when they do use these terms, **so code trust when a statement includes the word “trust” or trustworthiness when the statement includes “trustworthiness.”** Also code all forms of the terms (trusted, distrusted, trustworthy, etc.).

We have broadly defined each concept below and then provide several examples to further demonstrate how to code for each concept. The codes are not mutually exclusive, so you can add multiple codes to each response.

Codes and definitions

Overview: Below we provide the definitions that you will use for coding for the presence or absence of trust and trustworthiness in the interview data. These definitions will then be followed by rules to help guide how you apply them, some common examples, and then a short practice coding exercise. **Do not code until you have reviewed ALL of the material provided.** Check back to this document regularly while coding. The overall goal is to apply what is here in the codebook to the best of your ability, NOT to rely on your intuition/personal understanding of these concepts.

TRUST: **In the presence of uncertainty, the degree to which someone does or does not rely on, or put faith in, someone or something.** This definition of trust is purposefully broad, so as to capture the many different definitions and related dimensions of trust. Our definition of trust is designed to capture trust in all forms. This means we are not just interested in coding where trust is discussed as existing or being built but also in coding all the different ways trust could come up (See Trust coding rule #1).

TRUSTWORTHINESS: **An assessment of whether, why, or to what degree someone or something should or should not be trusted.** When paired with our definition of trust above, trustworthiness can also be thought of as **the degree to which someone believes someone or something should or should not be relied upon or given faith.** This definition is also purposefully broad, so as to capture all the different dimensions of trustworthiness that have been discussed in the literature.

Guidelines for identifying Trust and Trustworthiness

How are TRUST and TRUSTWORTHINESS different? The definition for trustworthiness and trust are very similar but carry different meanings, which we clarify in this section. **Trustworthiness** is a *perceived characteristic* of someone or something (e.g., a specific model, guidance, a developer), whereas **trust** is *relational* between an actor and someone or something.

Trustworthiness is *evaluative* (i.e., an assessment of someone or something), whereas the **trust** is *relational* (i.e., references to how the speaker/actor perceives or relates to someone or something).

How do you identify TRUST and TRUSTWORTHINESS? It can be difficult to look through a lot of rich data and identify these abstract concepts, so we came up with a set of guiding questions to help you identify potential instances of **Trust** and **Trustworthiness** and then help confirm your decision to code or not:

1. **Who/what? Who/what are they or are they not trusting?**
 - a. **Trust** requires both a trustor (the one doing the trusting) and a target of **Trust** (the thing or person being trusted). So ask yourself *who/what* is, is not, or is unsure about trusting *whom/what*?
 - b. **Trustworthiness** needs to be evaluated for something or someone, so ask yourself *who/what* is being evaluated/discussed with respect to **Trustworthiness**?
2. **Why/why not? Why/why not trust something or someone?**
 - a. **Trustworthiness** is evaluative and connected to **Trust**, so it inherently addresses the question of *why or why not Trust* something? So when looking for **Trustworthiness**, ask yourself *why* something may or may not be **Trusted**? Remember, **this needs to be an evaluation related to trust!**
3. **For what? What are they or are they not trusting someone or something for?**
 - a. **Trust** is generally discussed in connection with an outcome or action. In other words, what is the trustor **Trusting** (or not trusting) the trustee for? While there may be some examples of more general trust, most of the time there is an associated “*for what?*”

Rules for Coding

Below are several rules to follow when coding for both **Trust** and **Trustworthiness**:

1. **All forms of Trust and Trustworthiness should be coded.** By ‘forms’ we mean any discussion of trust or trustworthiness should be coded, whether it be positive, negative, or without a clear direction. Discussions of increasing, decreasing, or consistent levels of trust/trustworthiness should all also be coded. For example, mentions of trust could be discussed *positively* (e.g., trust being built, increased, promoted, established, or just already existing), *negatively* (e.g., trust being hurt, decreased, lowered, or lacking, as well as distrust and mistrust), or even in ways that are not clearly positive or negative (See rule #3). All of these discussions should be coded.
2. **If you code trustworthiness, also code trust.** Because we have defined trustworthiness and trust so broadly, it is impossible to discuss trustworthiness (an evaluation of trust) without also discussing trust in some way. We will tease out the differences between these topics later in inductive analyses, but for now we want to code inclusively. Note, if you code trust, you do not also code trustworthiness unless the criteria listed in the codebook apply.
3. **Discussions about being unsure/undecided and hypothetical discussions about trust and trustworthiness should be coded.** Code when an interviewee says they are unsure or undecided whether or not they **Trust** OR how **Trustworthy** someone or something is. Similarly, code when an interviewee is talking about what could or would theoretically be relevant for trust or trustworthiness.
4. **Trust and Trustworthiness can be coded for anyone or anything and be assigned by anyone or anything.** Trust can be assigned to anything, such as the AI/ML algorithm, model, developer. Similarly, anything can be evaluated as **Trustworthy** or not. Also, the “trustor” can be anyone or anything, but it is usually the interviewee.

5. **Do not code pre and post cursors of Trust and Trustworthiness:** We want to code direct mentions of trust and trustworthiness, not things that could lead to it or are impacts of it. We are coding the direct mentions only. In other words, don't try to "fill in the blanks" or make assumptions for the "why?" "who/what?" and "for what?" questions. Only code when the interviewee actually says them. Note, rule 5 does not 'cancel out' rule 3. Rule 5 is focused on limiting how much we, as coders, **infer** from the data. We want to be only coding what is **explicitly in the data**.
6. **When you code for one, double check for the other.** Trust and trustworthiness often co-occur, so make sure to look for the alternate code if you apply one.
7. **Descriptions should NOT be coded as trustworthiness unless they also have an evaluation of trust associated with them.** There is a difference between descriptions and evaluations. A forecaster can describe a lot of features but those alone are not necessarily **Trustworthiness**. There needs to be an evaluative component related to trust as well.
8. **If you're really torn on whether or not to code something - just code it.** We will be reviewing codes later and want to make sure we cast a wide net initially. We can always decide the code doesn't apply later.

Common codes to look for

Below are a set of common answers to the guiding questions: "who/what?", "why/why not?", and "for what?" Use these answers to help you identify **Trust** and **Trustworthiness** in the interview data. Note that these lists are NOT exhaustive. They are just meant to be a guide of common codes.

Common Who? and What? Who/what are they or are they not trusting? Answers :

1. **Guidance/models:** One of the most common targets of **Trust** and assessments of **Trustworthiness** is "guidance." What we mean by guidance is really anything forecasters are looking at when creating their forecasts, developing messaging, or for any other part of their job. This commonly includes specific models or tools.
 - a. **Examples:** HRRR, HREF, NAM, Euro, the guidance being used in the interview
2. **Forecast messages/forecaster communication:** Forecasters may also discuss the extent to which their core partners or members of the public do or do not **Trust** the communication, information, and messaging that the forecasters and/or their office put out. They may also discuss the **Trustworthiness** of this communication.
 - a. **Examples:** Social media posts, Decision support services or DSS packets, severe weather warnings/watches, updates on evolving weather events
3. **The forecast office and/or forecasters more generally:** Forecasters may also discuss how they themselves or their office is (or is not) **trusted** or perceived as **Trustworthy**. This includes discussions of "we" or "us" in the interview.
 - a. **Examples:** The National Weather Service, our office, forecasters

Common Why? Why/why not trust something or someone? Remember, this needs to be an evaluation related to trust! Answers:

1. **Performance/verification:** Forecasters may say the way something "performs" or has "verified" in the past is the reason they **Trust** (or do not **Trust**) something OR as the reason it is (or is not) **Trustworthy**. This is commonly discussed with respect to guidance of some sort (see Who? And What? #1). However, forecasters may not use these exact words, so we've included some synonyms for reference in addition to some examples.

- a. Examples: the model makes predictions in line with expectations, the model has previously had success in predicting events; the model performs well during a particular time frame, for particular environments, or under specific weather conditions
 - b. Synonyms for performance: has done well, works pretty good, does a solid job,
 - c. Synonyms for verification: usually checks out, nails the forecast, vibes well with reality
2. **Forecaster experience**: Another common reason forecasters say why they do or do not **Trust** something or why it is or is not **Trustworthy** comes from their past experiences with it. This generally covers having used something enough to know and trust it well.
 - a. Examples: the forecaster has used this guidance before for a particular application, the guidance is well-liked among other forecasters
 3. **Source/background**: Forecasters may **Trust** (or not **Trust**) something or assess it as **Trustworthy** based on where it came from or because of some of the background they know about it. This could be knowing who made the product or that it was given to them by a respected colleague.
 - a. Examples: using a model because it is created by a reputable source, using a model because it has been around for a long time and people continue to rely on it
 4. **Good presentation/ease of use**: Forecasters may mention **Trusting** (or not **Trusting**) or assess the **Trustworthiness** of something because of how it is presented (visually or through any other type of presentation). This could also include that guidance is easy to use or intuitive.
 - a. Examples: the model visualizes events clearly, the model is representative of reality

Common For what? What are you or are you not trusting someone or something for? Answers:

1. **To guide forecasting process**: A common answer to this question is to use/rely/lean on something (often guidance) to guide or inform the forecaster's process or work. This can be to provide them with useful, actionable, and accurate information that helps them do their job.
 - a. Examples: using a model to give a broad sense of conditions early on into an event, predict how a storm will evolve, give quality decision support.
 - b. Example from the data of what DOES count for this rule
 - i. **TRUST**: "And then, of course, within 48 hours I started looking pretty heavily at the HREF. Which is probably the thing I rely on the heaviest within 36 to 48 hours."
 - c. Example from the data of what does NOT count for this rule
 - i. **NOT TRUST**: "I was looking at the longer range and so, I looked at the European, the GFS, and the NAM to some extent."
 1. Note: This would not be coded because it's only clear that they *looked* at this guidance, we have no sense of if/how they relied on it or put faith in it.
2. **Forecasting in/for specific scenarios or types of events**: A more specific application of the above point is to help them with forecasting a specific instance or type of event.
 - a. Examples: to guide decisions early on or at a specific time range; to help inform the forecast for certain types of events (weakly forced, etc.)
3. **Providing effective and accurate communication/information**: Sometimes forecasters will talk about how communication, such as among the forecasters/forecaster offices, their core partners, and the public, is (or is not) trusted.
 - a. Examples: communicating future weather events, core partners relying on the information provided from the forecasters when making decisions.
 - b. NOTE: This can be tricky to determine, so **any mentions of people looking to the NWS for information or guidance should be coded as TRUST. Note, this rule does not apply for trustworthiness, this still should be considered like usual.** We will sort out these examples in more detail in the next stages of analysis

- c. Example from the data of what DOES count for this rule:
 - i. “We were getting a lot of calls about how bad it’s gonna be basically. ‘What should I do? Should I cancel this?’ Things like that.”
 - 4. **Performing job duties and responsibilities when there is clear uncertainty:** For this point we only want to capture instances where someone is clearly *trusting someone else to do their job* - not just their evaluations of how they did this job. For example, we don’t want to code something like “they did great on their first shift” as trust, but we do want to code trust if someone were to say “I was so busy that day and thought they could handle the work, so just let them go unsupervised.” The first example is just an evaluation, but the second shows trust in someone to do their job. One key thing that distinguishes the two is that there is *uncertainty* in the latter. We don’t know if the stand-in person will do a good job, but they are being relied on/believed in.
 - a. Example from the data of what DOES count for this rule:
 - i. **TRUST:** “Whereas I’m not necessarily going to drill down. You know, I’ll let them [points to the ‘floor’ where forecasters are working] do that. They’re the experts. Because I look at it every day, but I don’t look at it like they do when they’re producing a forecast. And so the briefings that I’m getting from them, you know, that tells the tale.”
 - b. Example from the data of what does NOT count for this rule:
 - i. **NOT TRUST:** “Well, we have defined roles for everybody. And I think everybody performed in their role, at least satisfactorily, or excellent.”
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Practice coding - a detailed guide to applying to codebook

In this section we will bring together all the definitions, coding rules, and common codes and show what this looks like. The image below shows the breakdown of between the interviewer's question, which is not coding but provides context for the answer, and the interviewee's answer, which is coded. The answer is broken down into the unit of coding, a statement, which is a section of text that is connected to one topic (as discussed on page 1).

Interviewer (question): As a forecaster, we know that you work in such an information rich environment, you have so many tools and guidance at your fingertips. So why do you choose to use what you do use?

Do not code the question.

Forecaster (answer): I think it's a good question. I mean, I honestly I think you trust it, you know, if you've you, if you have a process, and you've done it for a while, and it's worked for you, you start to trust it. And I think that's where the challenge is, you know, and I've noticed it in myself as you get further in your career, infusing some of this newer stuff into your process that you've created over so long.

Codes are applied to each statement of the the answer, not the whole answer.

There are some forecasters that have been around a long time that are very good at that. They take new information and kind of are able to sink it into their process and there are others that still will just look at the Nam and the Euro and the GFS and that's their three models, and that's worked for them for 30 years and that's what they're gonna do. So I think that's kind of where I was going with that. You know, it's just worked for you in the past that you'll continue to use it.

But that being said, I know. For me sometimes if a product especially on the kind of looks. I don't know, swanky looks, it looks like it has a good presentation to it. For some reason, I find myself trusting it more. And it doesn't make any sense versus like if you go into a website and it looks old. It looks like not the visualizations aren't good, you're not as likely to trust something that just looks clean and crisp. And you can find the data that you want easily. It doesn't make a lot of sense, but it's true, I think, for a lot of people.

Interviewer (question): As a forecaster, we know that you work in such an information-rich environment, you have so many tools and guidance at your fingertips. So why do you choose to use what you do use?

Forecaster (answer): *I think it's a good question. I mean, I honestly I think you trust it, you know, if you've you, if you have a process, and you've done it for a while, and it's worked for you, you start to trust it. And I think that's where the challenge is, you know, and I've noticed it in myself as you get further in your career, infusing some of this newer stuff into your process that you've created over so long.*

- **Code for Trust**
 - Actor: Forecaster
 - Target: guidance/model ("it")
 - For what? To guide forecasting process ("if you have a process, and you've done it for a while, and it's worked for you")
- **Code for Trustworthiness**
 - What is being evaluated: Guidance/model ("it")
 - Why is it being trusted: Forecaster experience ("it's worked for you, you start to trust it.")

There are some forecasters that have been around a long time that are very good at that. They take new information and kind of are able to sink it into their process and there are others that still will just

look at the Nam and the Euro and the GFS and that's their three models, and that's worked for them for 30 years and that's what they're gonna do. So I think that's kind of where I was going with that. You know, it's just worked for you in the past that you'll continue to use it.

- **Code for Trust**
 - Actor: Forecasters
 - Targets: Guidance/model (NAM, Euro, GFS)
 - For what? To guide forecasting process (“sink it into their process”, “that's worked for them for 30 years and that's what they're gonna do.”)
- **Code for Trustworthiness**
 - What is being evaluated: guidance/model (NAM/Euro/GFS)
 - Why is it being trusted: forecaster experience (“that's worked for them for 30 years and that's what they're gonna do.”, “it's just worked for you in the past that you'll continued to use it.”)

But that being said, I know. For me sometimes if a product especially on the kind of looks. I don't know, swanky looks, it looks like it has a good presentation to it. For some reason, I find myself trusting it more. And it doesn't make any sense versus like if you go into a website and it looks old. It looks like not the visualizations aren't good, you're not as likely to trust something that just looks clean and crisp. And you can find the data that you want easily. It doesn't make a lot of sense, but it's true, I think, for a lot of people.

- **Code for Trust**
 - Actor: Forecaster
 - Target: Guidance/model (“it”)
 - For what? To guide forecasting process (“find the data that you want easily”)
- **Code for Trustworthiness**
 - What is being evaluated? Guidance/model (“it”)
 - Why is it being trusted? Good presentation/ease of use (“you're not as likely to trust something that just looks clean and crisp. And you can find the data that you want easily.”)